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Malaria fever and patients with sickle cell anemia: a retrospective study

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ABSTRACT

Sickle cell disease is a hereditary condition that poses a significant health risk in tropical Africa, and it has been observed that this condition can worsen in conjunction with malaria. Therefore, this study used a retrospective cohort design to analyze malaria fever occurrences in patients with or without sickle cell disease who were admitted to Ifako Ijaye General Hospital in Lagos State, Nigeria, between 2017 and 2020. The findings reveal that 52.5% of the total admitted patients were male, while 47.5% were female. The age distribution shows that 49.2% of the patients were 1-10 years old, making it the largest percentage, followed by the 11-20 years at 30.3%. The admission rates for malaria were 17.0% in 2017, 23.2% in 2018, 21.1% in 2019, and peaked at 38.7% in 2020, representing the highest proportion of admitted patients. The mortality analysis indicated that 55.7% of the deceased patients were male, while 44.3% were female. A significant majority of the mortality cases, 85.8%, were among children aged 1-10 years, highlighting that this demographic is the most susceptible to malaria, regardless of gender. While the number of patients with sickle cell anaemia was lower among the admitted malaria cases, they accounted for a significant portion of the mortality rate compared to those without sickle cell disease.

Keywords: Malaria Fever, Patients, Sickle Cell Anemia, Medical Facilities

1. INTRODUCTION

Plasmodium parasites cause malaria, a fever that is transmitted to humans through the bite of a female Anopheles mosquito. The World Health Organization (WHO) reported approximately 241 million cases and 627,000 deaths globally in 2020 (WHO, 2022). In Sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, malaria is known to cause the death of a child under the age of five every two minutes (Abdullahi and Abubakar, 2019). Symptoms of malaria typically appear seven days or more after infection, usually between 10 and 15 days. These symptoms include fever, headache, chills, and vomiting, which can be mild and difficult to distinguish from other illnesses.

Severe manifestations of malaria may include anaemia, respiratory distress due to metabolic acidosis, and cerebral malaria, particularly common in children with severe cases (Ruiz Lopez *et al.*, 2014).

Haemoglobinopathies such as sickle cell trait (HbAS) and haemoglobin C trait (HbAC) are believed to provide some protection against the severe and life-threatening manifestations of malaria (Taylor *et al.*, 2013; WHO, 2018). While these genetic variants do not eliminate the risk of contracting malaria, they can significantly reduce the severity of the infection (Taylor *et al.*, 2012). The human spleen plays a crucial role in the immunity developed after repeated malaria infections (Ehimen *et al.*, 2013) and serves as the central site for clearing malaria parasites from the body. In individuals with reduced splenic function, clearance of the parasites may take longer. Additionally, the hyposplenism associated with sickle cell anaemia may explain why the protective effect against malaria is diminished in these individuals (Buffet *et al.*, 2011).

Sickle cell disease is a significant public health concern caused by a mutation in the gene responsible for producing the β -globin. This mutation results in the haemoglobin (Hb)S allele, which contrasts with the wild-type HbA allele (Piel *et al.*, 2013). Individuals who are homozygous for this mutation develop a serious condition known as sickle cell anaemia, which was almost always fatal before the introduction of modern therapies (Ehimen *et al.*, 2013).

Approximately 20 to 25 million people around the world are affected by sickle cell disease, with an estimated 12 to 15 million living in Sub-Saharan Africa. Each year, around 300,000 infants are born with this gene (Akingbola *et al.*, 2014).

People all over the world are affected by this disease, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa, India, the Mediterranean region, and Southern European countries. The disease has also spread to the Caribbean, as well as South and North America, and Northern Europe due to both ancient and contemporary population migrations (Adegoke *et al.*, 2017). It is crucial to assess the prevalence, risk factors, and potential outcomes of this disease, especially because an immune-compromised individual's exposure to malaria can lead to severe co-morbid conditions that may result in mortality.

2. METHODOLOGY

2. 1. Study Design

The study utilized a hospital-based retrospective cohort design conducted at General Hospital, Ifako Ijaye, Alagbado, Lagos State. Data from patients admitted between January 2017 and December 2020 were collected, reviewed, and analyzed.

2. 2. Ethical Consent / Approval

After the purpose of the study was communicated, administrative approval was obtained from the director of the General Hospital, Ifako Ijaye, Nigeria.

2. 3. Study groups and Procedure

A study was carried out on malaria in patients with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) and those with Non-Sickle Cell Anaemia (nSCD). The participants, ranging in age from 1 to 45 years, had a recorded history of malaria. The study group was recruited using hospital admission records, with the sociodemographic information linked with malaria fever in Sickle Cell disease and Non-Sickle Cell disease patients extracted using the record's entry form. Data validation and verification were carried out to eliminate duplication of records and to ensure that the data could be used for analysis.

2. 4. Data Management and Analysis

The data collected was entered into a Microsoft Excel 2016 spreadsheet and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software, version 21. We determined the frequency distribution through cross-tabulation and assessed the association between variables using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The significance level was set at 0.05.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Demography of Admitted Malaria Patients

The demographic characteristics of patients admitted with malaria are summarized in Table 1. The results indicate that a total of 24,599 patients (52.5%) were male, while 22,267 patients (47.5%) were female (Figure 1). Among the age groups, 23,043 patients (49.2%) were between the ages of 1-10 years, representing the highest percentage. This was followed by the 11-20 age group, which accounted for 14,212 patients (30.3%). Furthermore, 9,497 patients (20.3%) were aged 21-30 years, while only 89 patients (0.2%) fell within the 31-40 age group. The lowest percentage was seen in patients over the age of 40, which represented 25 patients (0.1%) (Figure 2).

Table 1. Demography of Admitted Patients with Malaria Fever.

Characteristics	Frequency (%)	ANOVA	
		F	P value
Gender			
Male	24,599 (52.5)	6.45	0.08
Female	22,267 (47.5)		
Age group			
1-10 years	23,043 (49.2)	26.4	0.04*

11-20 years	14,212 (30.3)		
21-30 years	9,497 (20.3)		
31-40 years	89 (0.2)		
> 40 years	25 (0.1)		
Admission Year			
2017	7,952 (17.0)	3.17	0.07
2018	10,874 (23.2)		
2019	9,890 (21.1)		
2020	18,150 (38.7)		
Sickle Cell Disease			
Yes	2,158 (4.6)	63.4	0.02*
No	44,708 (95.4)		

*Values asterisked are significant at $p < 0.05$

Figure 1. Gender percentage of admitted malaria patients from 2017-2020.

Figure 2. Age group percentage admitted for malaria disease from 2017-2020.

Figure 3. Trends of malaria disease cases from 2017 to 2020.

Figure 4. Percentage of malaria patients with sickle cell disease and those without..

The trend in malaria admissions from 2017 to 2020 is shown in Figure 3. In 2017, 7,952 patients (17.0%) were admitted; in 2018, this number rose to 10,874 patients (23.2%). The year 2019 saw 9,890 patients (21.1%) admitted, while 2020 recorded the highest number of admissions at 18,150 patients (38.7%). The trend of admissions across these years was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, Figure 4 illustrates the percentage of admitted malaria patients regarding sickle cell disease. Out of all patients, 44,708 (95.4%) did not have sickle cell disease, while 2,158 patients (4.6%) were affected by the blood disorder. The difference in the number of patients with sickle cell disease compared to those without was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

3. 1. 1. Malaria Patient Mortality

The mortality status of patients with malaria is presented in Table 2 and Figure 5. The results indicate that 59 patients (55.7%) were male, while 47 patients (44.3%) were female. Among the age groups, 91 patients (85.8%) were aged 1-10 years, which had the highest mortality percentage, while 15 patients (14.2%) were aged 11-20 years (as shown in Figure 6).

The trend of malaria-related mortality from 2017 to 2020 is depicted in Figure 7. It reveals that 18 patients (16.9%) died in 2017, 28 patients (26.4%) in 2018, 15 patients (14.2%) in 2019, and 45 patients (42.5%) in 2020. Figure 8 shows that 83 patients (78.3%) did not have sickle cell disease, while 23 patients (21.7%) were battling this blood disorder. The differences in mortality rates across the years were statistically significant, with a p-value of less than 0.05.

Figure 5. Percentage mortality between genders.

Figure 6. Mortality percentage between age groups.

Figure 7. Number of mortality across the years.

Figure 8. Percentage of mortality between non-sickle cell disease. and sickle cell disease patients.

Table 2. Mortality status of patients with malaria disease.

Characteristics	Mortality (%)	ANOVA	
		F	P value
Gender			
Male	59 (55.7)	6.02	0.13
Female	47 (44.3)		
Age group			
1-10 years	91 (85.8)	10.6	0.04*
11-20 years	15 (14.2)		
21-30 years	-		
31- 40 years	-		
> 40 years	-		
Admission Year			
2017	18 (16.9)	3.68	0.06
2018	28 (26.4)		
2019	15 (14.2)		
2020	45 (42.5)		
Sickle Cell Disease			
Yes	83 (78.3)	9.30	0.04*
No	23 (21.7)		

*Values asterisked are significant at $p < 0.05$

4. DISCUSSION

The majority of patients admitted in the study were male, comprising 52.5% of the total population. This finding aligns with the study by Aloni *et al.* (2013), which reported that male patients accounted for 58.9% of admissions. Similarly, Lagunju and Brown (2013) found a male-to-female ratio of 1.6:1 in their study populations from the Democratic Republic of Congo and Nigeria, where males made up 61.2% of the cases. This suggests that both males and females should be equally involved in prevention programs. The largest age group among the patients were young individuals aged 1 to 20 years, representing 79.5% of the total population.

This is understandable, as children in Sub-Saharan Africa are believed to be at an increased risk of malaria morbidity and mortality (Eleonore *et al.*, 2020).

There was a significant increase in malaria cases (from 17% to 38.7%) between the years 2017 and 2020. This rise may be attributed to Nigeria's high prevalence of malaria, which accounts for 25% of the global burden (Diallo *et al.*, 2019), as well as increased exposure to mosquito bites due to lifestyle factors such as the non-use of insecticide-treated nets and other available control measures. Additionally, a small proportion of the admitted malaria patients (4.6%) were also suffering from sickle cell disease. This finding supports the work of Eleonore *et al.*, (2020), who reported that 22% of sickle cell disease cases were noted compared to non-sickle cell disease patients in a study conducted in Cameroon.

According to the World Health Organization (2018), on global health day, malaria is responsible for child mortality every two minutes in sub-Saharan Africa. A total of 106 mortality cases were recorded, with the majority (55.7%) being male. The mortality rate from malaria in this study showed a significant increase, rising from 16.9% in 2017 to 42.5% in 2020. The noticeable spike in mortality in 2020 can be attributed to various factors, including the global pandemic (COVID-19), which likely led to reduced attention to existing illnesses and complications in patients.

Children aged 1 to 10 experienced the majority of malaria-related deaths, accounting for 8.58% of the total. This aligns with reports from the WHO (2018) and Eleonore *et al.*, (2020), which indicate that children represent a major population affected by malaria mortality. According to Tshilolo *et al.*, (2007), severe malaria is a leading cause of morbidity in patients with sickle cell disease. In this study, 21.7% of the mortality cases were among individuals suffering from sickle cell disease, which is a significant proportion compared to those without it. It is established that malaria exacerbates hemolytic anaemia in patients with sickle cell disease (Adekeye *et al.*, 2024).

5. CONCLUSION

The results of the study confirm that children are the most vulnerable population to malaria, affecting both boys and girls, which indicates that preventive measures are needed for all. Patients with sickle cell anaemia were found to be underrepresented among admitted malaria cases; however, they had a significantly higher mortality rate compared to those without sickle cell disease. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that a larger number of hospitals be involved in future research to obtain more comprehensive data. Furthermore, the high susceptibility of sickle cell patients to malaria should be communicated to the public to promote prevention against mosquito bites.

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